

Synthesis and biological activity of copper(II) mixed ligand complexes with thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone as the primary ligand

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The complexing ability of thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (L) has been investigated. Copper complexes of the type CuLL₁ have been prepared, where L₁ = salicylaldehyde/salicylaldoxime/salicylaldehyde semicarbazone/salicylaldehyde phenylhydrazone/salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone/8-hydroxyquinoline/2-hydroxypyridine. The complexes have a square - planar structure. The antibacterial activities of these complexes have also been studied.

Though the simple metal complexes of thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone have already been known¹, including a very recent report² wherein the biological properties of copper(II) complex has been reported, there is no work on the mixed ligand complexes involving thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone as a primary ligand. The present communication describes the synthesis and biological activity of some copper(II) mixed ligand complexes with thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone as the primary ligand.

Results and Discussion

Several mixed ligand copper(II) complexes involving thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (L) as a primary ligand and salicylaldehyde (SalH), salicylaldoxime (SaloH), salicylaldehyde semicarbazone (SalscH), salicylaldehyde phenylhydrazone (SalphH), salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (SalTscH), 8-hydroxyquinoline (OxineH) and 2-hydroxypyridine (2-PyOH) as secondary ligands have been prepared leading to metal complexes of the type CuLL₁, where L is thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone and L₁ the secondary ligand. All the complexes (Table 1) are colored and partially soluble in chloroform and acetonitrile. Thermogravimetric studies indicate that they do not contain any water molecule and are thermally quite stable. The expected transition ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, 2E_g in a D_{4h} environment for mixed ligand complexes are masked by CT bands in the UV-region. The disappearance of the band due to NH-C=S upon complexation and the appearance of a new band for the azine nitrogen and the thiolosulfur of the ligand (Table 1) along with the negative shift (20–25 cm⁻¹) of the ligand C=N band observed in the complexes, all indicate the involvement of azomethine

nitrogen in complexation³. This is supported by a positive shift (15–20 cm⁻¹) of the ligand N=N band on coordination with the metal ion. Hence, the structure of the complexes may be a five-membered chelate.

Table 1. Magnetic and IR spectral data of the copper(II) complexes*

Compd (Colour)	μ_{eff} B.M	ν_{NH} cm ⁻¹	$\nu_{C-N-N-C}$ cm ⁻¹	ν_{N-N} cm ⁻¹	ν_{C-S} cm ⁻¹
CuL ₂ (Green)	1.92	3323	1573	1052	705
CuL(Sal) (Green)	1.90	3323	1501	1054	705
CuL(Salo) (Green)	1.92	3324	1574	1052	749
CuL(Salph) (Green)	1.88	3342	1573	1071	738
CuL(Salsc) (Brown)	1.82	3362	1613	1013	752
CuL(SalTsc) (Brown)	1.80	3284	1554	1052	747
CuL(Oxine) (Green)	1.90	3320	1578	1054	744
CuL(2-pyo) (Yellow)	1.90	3354	1573	1052	759

*All complexes did not melt sharply, decomposing above 200°

The antibacterial studies of the synthesized copper(II) complexes were determined by disk-diffusion method (filter-paper disks) against microorganisms *Klebsiella arogers*, *Proteus* species, *Pseudomonas* species, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi*. Compared to the primary ligand copper(II) complex, some of the mixed ligand complexes are active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Thus CuL(SalTsc) is active against both *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, while CuL(oxine) and CuL(Salo) are active against *S. aureus* alone. This work assumes importance as many metal-thiosemicarbazone complexes are found to have significant antitubercular, fungicidal⁴ and antitumor⁵ activities.

Experimental

Bis[thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazanato]copper(II) : A mixture of solutions of thiophene-2-car-

Note

boxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone³ (1.85 g, 10 mmol) in aqueous acetone (1 : 1; 200 ml) and a solution of copper(II) acetate (1 g, 5 mmol) in aqueous acetone (1 : 1; 200 ml) was allowed to stand overnight. The resulting complex was washed with aqueous acetone (1 : 1), dried in air and then in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Mixed ligand complexes : To a solution of the primary ligand thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone³ (1.85 g, 10 mmol) and the secondary ligand (10 mmol) in aqueous acetone (1 : 1; 400 ml) was added a solution of copper(II) acetate (2 g, 10 mmol) in aqueous acetone (1 : 1; 200 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The resulting complex was washed with aqueous acetone (1 : 1), dried in air and then in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. Purity of the complexes was tested by TLC.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy type

magnetic balance at room temperature (303–308 K). Electronic spectra (nujol/acetonitrile) were measured on a Shimadzu UV 160 spectrophotometer.

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